

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
COMMUNITIES

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ABBREVIATIONS LIST

Abbreviation	Meaning
KPI / KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
SMEs	Small Medium Enterprises
WP	Work Package
MS	Milestone
D	Deliverable
M	Month
TSIG	TOYLABS Special Interest Group
AEFJ	Asociacion Española de Fabricante de Juguetes

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this deliverable is to report all the dissemination tools and activities developed and implemented in the first reporting period and an updated plan for the next phases of the project.

The report includes a description of all the activities including objectives, content and impact of each of them. In particular, ToyLabs communication and dissemination activities include:

- The ToyLabs public website that includes all the relevant information of the project including news and public deliverables
- The newsletter created according with the main outcomes and milestones of the project
- Social media channels to reach a wide audience and engage potential stakeholders
- The ToyLabs blog, published in the news section of the website, it includes blog posts related to the main outcomes of the project presenting the information in a more accessible way
- Communication material: brochures, posters, promotional gifts, etc to be brought at events, all created personalized to an specific target audience to meet their expectations.
- Participation in events: the partners in the consortium have attended and presented toylabs in many events. The main events include:
 - Spielwarenmesse 2017. Nuremberg Toy Show and exhibition
 - Maker Faire. Vienna
 - The 16th International Trade Fair For Toys & Preschool Educational Resources
 - Fall Toy Preview 2017 in Dallas USA
 - Spiel International 2017
 - PROGRAMA INMERSIÓN DIGITAL EMPRESARIAL (IDE) - REALIDAD VIRTUAL Y AUMENTADA
 - AEFJ Preshow Juguetes 2017
- Scientific publications are being developed to disseminate the project among the scientific community
- Various synergies with projects have been established including in some cases joint activities
- Description of the internal dissemination performed by each partner in their own organization network

The dissemination plan includes the prevision of activities and main guideline for the next phases of the project. Including main events to be attended, publications, etc,

1 INTRODUCTION

The dissemination of the concept, activities and results of the Project is one of the most important phases of a research and innovation project. The main objective is to raise awareness of the project towards the interested stakeholders and properly communicate the results of the project.

To ensure the achievement of these objectives, several communication and dissemination tools have been developed. All the activities have been designed to ensure the proper communication of the project outcomes to the right audiences in the most effective way possible.

The following sections include the first period report of dissemination and communication and the updated plan.

The report includes a profound description of all the undertaken activities including the objectives, content and impact of each action. In the case of the updated plan, it includes the description of the activities for the next phases of the project in a more specific way than the early plan in D6.1

2 COMMUNICATION MECHANISMS

2.1 TOYLABS WEBSITE

The ToyLabs Website was created soon after the beginning of the project, it is available at <http://toylabs.eu/>

The toylabs.eu project website was built and is maintained by NTUA. The website's content is kept up to date by SILO.

2.1.1 Purpose

Nowadays, a public website represents one of the main communication media allowing a fast and accessible communication of any kind of information to a vast audience. An accessible website offers the possibility to any stakeholder to get in touch with the project and it allows to create awareness by having all the important information available and organized.

The website was designed in the most appropriate way to present all the public information in a clear and accessible manner. Always having in mind the main search engines and a list of keywords to ensure the visibility.

This action had two main purposes: offer easy access to the relevant information of the project to create interest and facilitate the communication between interested stakeholders and the consortium.

For the first objective, all the public information has been displayed in the website including information about the project in general, the consortium, objectives of the project and work structure. To provide more in-depth information all public deliverables are available in the website. In addition, news and blogposts related to the progress of the project were also published in the website.

To ensure the easy communication with the consortium, the contact information is available on the website apart from links to the social media channels used.

2.1.2 Structure

ToyLabs' website is structured in different pages to offer clear and organised content. In the following each section and its content is briefly described

Figure 1 ToyLabs website Sections

As the first contact with any visitor, the Home Page offers a brief description of the basic information of the project. At the top there is a banner with some of the most relevant content in the website, as you scroll down you can find a brief description of the project scope, the consortium, links to the news and blogposts, the expected outcomes of the project, etc.

The contact page includes a contact form and the contact information, this page represents a direct and easy way to contact the consortium for those interested and get more information.

The news section represents a space where any relevant milestone or event is posted, it includes blogposts explaining different parts of the project and the progress on the different tasks and the newsletters. The blog posts and news have been created with the collaboration of all partners. In this section the visitor can really be aware of the evolution of the project in a more accessible manner.

The project info section explains with more detail the scope of the project explaining how ToyLabs will change the toy developing methodology by introducing a co creation platform with different actors. Here it is possible to find four subsections: consortium, deliverables, objectives/goal and work structure. In the consortium section you can find a description of the different organisations participating together to develop the project, it also includes a link to their organisation website. All the public deliverables form the project such as reports or demonstrable are available in a dedicated space, this way is possible get full information form the project development. In the objectives and goals section you can find in depth information about the scientific, technical and business objectives.

The next section is a special page dedicated to the ToyLabs Special Interest Group (TSIG), where interested people or organisation can apply.

The web page also provides links to social media and a way to join the mailing list.

2.1.3 Visibility of Website

To ensure the effectiveness of the website, it has been designed and structured so it is shown in the first results for different search engines.

Through social media, many visitors that are interested in the profile and want to get more information in a website, for this reason all the social media channels have access to the public project's website

2.2 NEWSLETTER

2.2.1 Purpose

The main purpose of the newsletter is to provide information about milestones and activities performed within the project. Different issues are created when there is a relevant information or important advances to transmit.

2.2.2 Structure

The structure of each newsletter is modified depending on the needs of each issue.

The main structure includes general information about the project: description of the purpose of the project, partners, duration, etc. This information is consistent in every issue of the newsletter.

The rest of the content is organised depending on the information to be published in each specific issue. The basic structure is presented in the template bellow.

Figure 2 Newsletter Template

2.2.3 Distribution

The newsletters are distributed in an electronic format to the interested stakeholders and through the internal network of each organization in the consortium and anyone interested in receive information of the project.

The newsletters are also available on the website to be downloaded.

2.3 SOCIAL MEDIA

Various accounts in different social media channels were created by AIJU and NTUA at the start of the project. The maintenance of social media has been carried out by Singular Logic and AIJU.

2.3.1 Purpose

Having active social media channels helps disseminate the project to large audiences and increase awareness about the project between different target audiences.

Social media profiles have become the most direct and fast communication channel between the public and the organization, in this case the project consortium. Those interested in the project can easily ask for information or contact us in a more interactive way through the comments in a publication or even more directly via chat.

Apart from this, social media channels are the easiest way to keep the audience informed continuously about the project development.

2.3.2 Frequency and content

In order to be able to plan and schedule the publications in different social media the platform Buffer is being used. Through this platform is possible to schedule publications for the different social media channels so the content is consistent.

Social media post vary depending in the information to be shared. The content could be classified in shared articles, ToyLabs Blogpost, ToyLabs Events and other relevant information of the project.

Relevant posts have been boosted in order to reach larger audiences and ensure the visibility of the action, in particular the TSIG open call. The boosted post has been proven effective regarding the people reached.

Figure 3 TSIG boosted post

2.3.3 Followers and interactions

During the first 9 months of the project, Toylabs achieved to establish an active presence, raise awareness for the project and engage a targeted audience.

The following table presents certain metrics regarding social media dissemination. The metrics as recorded are based on Facebook and Twitter presence as the rest of the social media channels (eg Slideshare, ResearchGate) is planned to be utilised appropriately after the 1st release of the platform in order to disseminate actual facts and results.

Metric	Achieved
TOYLABS entries in the social media accounts	111
Social Media Followers	129
Impressions	16151
Engagements	315
Link Clicks	56

Table 1 Social media metrics

Further, interesting insights can be drawn from Facebook Insights concerning the profiles of the followers of the Toylabs account. As depicted in the following figures, the great majority of followers are men, between 25-44, while for the women the age group is narrower as the majority belongs to the group 24-34.

The people who follow your Page

Figure 4 Gender and Age of followers

In general the consortium is aware that the aforementioned insights, although they refer to facebook and twitter only, shall be further improved in order to consider the Toylabs social media presence as really successful.

However given that in the first half of the project, most of the work performed is internal work, producing results which cannot be easily engage people in the social media, the consortium expects that the situation in the second half of the project will change dramatically.

Having the platform released is the most crucial part, together with the promotion of the various dissemination activities which are performed in the fairs and exhibitions that Toylabs partners participate which are all taking place in the last 3-4 months of each calendar year.

Given the above and even though the targets set in the DoA are optimistic, the consortium strongly believes that by the end of the project the desired values of the social media dissemination metrics will have been achieved.

2.4 TOYLABS BLOG

The blog posts are available in ToyLabs website www.toylabs.eu in the section news.

2.4.1 Purpose

Following with the aim of keeping the interested audience informed and involving new people in the project, the blog posts are a way to accomplish this objective.

The blog posts intent to inform the audience on the different milestones and development of the project by giving specific information in an easy to access format so the different target groups, including non-professional, can easily follow with the project.

2.4.2 Structure

ToyLabs blog was intended to reach a wide audience including a variety of target audiences (professional and non-professional). Therefore, the information had to be presented in a summarized and easy to understand manner.

All posts were accompanied with a picture, table or graphic to help illustrate the information presented in the article.

2.4.3 Frequency and responsible

All the posts where scheduled at the start of the project and a different responsible was established for each post according to the content. All partners have participated in the creation of the blog posts related to their tasks. The collection and publishing has been handled by NTUA.

The next table shows the different posts that have already been posted and the responsible team for each one.

Title	Description	Date	State	Responsible
01. ToyLabs project introduction	Introduction to the Project	30/03/2017	Completed	NTUA
02. Toy Creation process	Description of the toy creation process in the DoA	06/04/2017	Completed	AIJU
03. Key challenges of the Toy industry	Key Challenges as taken from the DoA	09/04/2017	Completed	AIJU
04. High Level Description of the ToyLabs Methodology	High Level Methodology extracted from the DoA	27/04/2017	Completed	NTUA
05. ToyLabs Pilot	Introduction fo Pilot Case #1	02/07/2017	Completed	V-CUBES
06. ToyLabs Pilot 2 – Dolls & Accessories Pilot	Introduction of Pilot Case #2	12/07/2017	Completed	JUEMA
07. Expected Impact of the ToyLabs methodology and platform	Expected Impact from DoA	18/07/2017	Completed	SLG
08. ToyLabs Open Innovation and Cocreation Integrated Methodology	Most important parts of D2.1	24/07/2017	Completed	NTUA
09. The ToyLabs Platform - Early Insights on our Development	Things taken out of D3.1	27/07/2017	Completed	SLG
10. Market Analytics and Trends Analysis in ToyLabs	Input from T2.2	03/08/2017	Completed	NTUA
11. The ToyLabs Platform v1 - Mockups and Designs	Mockups and Stuff from D3.2	30/08/2017	Completed	SLG

12. ToyLabs Pilots KickOff	Input from D5.1	28/09/2017	Completed	AIJU
13. Augmented Reality for End User Feedback in ToyLabs	Input from T2.3	26/10/2017	Completed	SLG

Table 2 Published Blogposts

2.4.4 Publishing

All the blogposts have been published in the news section of the website and the link was shared in social media to increase the reach.

In order to gather further attention and reach a bigger audience, all the blog posts have been shared in the different social media channels. This posts included a short and catchy description of the content of the blog and the link to the actual post in the website.

2.5 COMMUNICATION MATERIAL

The communication material is an easy way to provide instant information about the project, it is useful in fairs and events where the different material help to bring attention to the project and give information to those interested, the main point is to give essential information to get people interested in the topic and contact information including the website where more in depth information can be found.

Different versions and materials have been created to be used in fairs and events, many of the materials have been personalized depending on the type of event and on the assistants to offer quality information of the interest of the target audience.

For this same reason, as the project has many target audience groups with different interests in the project, the dissemination material has been created so it can be easily modified and the information can be adapted to each case.

2.5.1 Brochures factsheets and banners

Different versions have been created depending on the objective and the audience of the event where they were going to be delivered. The objective of those is to give fast and clear information to the target audience and get them interested in the project.

The reason to create different versions is to be able to adapt the information to the interests of the audience and the type of event so they are more effective in getting people interested in the project.

A first brochure was created at the start of the project with very general information and the information contact. The main scope of the information was to present the idea of a new business model for toy industry SMEs and the introduction of FabLabs and additive manufacturing in the process. The objective was to give a general idea of the project and introduce a call to action "contact us and we will keep you informed" so anyone interested would contact the consortium or find more information in the website.

Figure 5 First Brochure

Another brochure was created mainly addressed to toy manufacturers but it is easily adaptable to any other stakeholders. It presents a description of the ToyLabs new methodology and how it improves the toy development process along with a general description and contact information. The aim of this brochure is to make toy manufacturers aware of the improvements this collaborative platform offers to the design and development of new toys and how this could affect their companies.

Figure 6 Toy Manufacturers brochure

A simple banner was created to include in the partner’s e-mail signature. This is a very basic banner that was completed with the website and contact information.

Figure 7 toyLabs basic Banner

2.5.2 Poster & Roll up

In order to stand out in the different events and grab assistants' attention a general poster was created. The information includes only a general description of the project and contact information as the poster does not intent to inform but to encourage people to contact the consortium and ask for more information.

The poster has been used in several events hanging in the ToyLabs representative partner's booth. It resulted to be a very useful tool to catch attention as many visitors found the concept interesting and asked for more information.

Figure 8 ToyLabs Poster

Following the same objective, a roll up was designed as a more versatile format, as it can be easily set up in many places and can be used multiple times for many different events. For this reason, the information has also been kept minimal, only a description of the project and contact information. The objective with this material is not so much to inform but to get people interested in the concept so they ask for more information or find it in the website.

Figure 9 ToyLabs rollup

2.5.3 Promotional material

For promotion in events different promotional materials were created so they could act as gifts to attendants or to showcase the project in a less conventional way.

Both FabLabs created a small version of the logo in different materials such as wood and Plexiglas, using available technology in their facilities. These little gifts are a great way to attract people and give them something else than a business card or a brochure that will make them remember the project and find more information

On its side JUEMA dressed up a doll representative of the company with Cloths with the ToyLabs project logo that became a great way to attract visitors to their booth and get them interested in the project. The doll was chosen because it is what best represents the company and the reason of their involvement in the project.

Figure 10 Promotional material

3 DISSEMINATION MECHANISMS

3.1 PARTICIPATION IN EVENTS

Representatives from the consortium have attended different events since the start of the project to ensure contact with external parties and make them aware of the project and its purpose. The dissemination carried out in each event has varied depending on the type of event and the stage of the project. The events are selected according to the main topic and the assistants' profiles. In the following the events attended are explained.

Spielwarenmesse 2017

Event information

Title: Spielwarenmesse

Nuremberg, February 2017

Participation: V-Cubes

Action: Presentation to visitors

Attendees

Last February 2017 V-Cubes attended Spielwarenmesse, the biggest Toy Show and Exhibition globally. During the event V-Cubes as representatives of ToyLabs consortium introduced and discussed the project with 8 European and 3 American Toy makers.

Maker Faire Vienna

Event information

Title: Maker Faire

20-21 May 2017 Vienna

Participation: FabLab Romania

Material: Brochure, keychain gift

Action: Presentation of the project concept, distribution of flyers, contact with event organizers

Attendees: 900 makers

<http://www.makerfairevienna.com/>

FabLab Bucharest participated as visitor in the fair but had the opportunity to talk to all the exhibitors and give out flyers.

In the event other FabLabs, amateur toymakers and a large number of participants were contacted. In total, over 50 participants were informed about the project including FabLabs and Toy Makers, who showed great interest in the project.

The ToyLabs concept was presented and around 300 flyers were handed. The assistants were also asked their opinion on the idea and if they would be interested in being part of the network.

All of the FabLabs expressed an interest in the project and even volunteered to be part of a test run when the platform is launched.

The amateur toymakers were very interested in the project. By amateur, it's meant people who develop games but do not have a toy making company. They were very interested in making their toys up to safety standards but they didn't know what those were. A very different approach these people had to their product is that they also wanted to make DIY plans available for free but also sell a finished product.

Most people contacted showed interest in the project, mostly because they were intrigued by the word "toy".

The 16th International Trade Fair For Toys & Preschool Educational Resources

Event information

Title: *The 16th International Trade Fair For Toys & Preschool Educational Resources*

Date/Place: Shanghai New International Expo Centre. 18-20 October 2017

Participation: Paola Reina as representatives of JUEMA

Material: Brochure, presentation, poster

Action: exhibition of the brand at the booth. Innovations in doll making and traditional ways of doll manufacturing

Attendees: 65450 visitors. Local and International distributors

<http://www.china-toy-expo.com/en/>

ToyLabs was represented by toy company Paola Reina (JUEMA) in the 16th International Trade Fair For Toys & Preschool Educational Resources held in Shanghai from the 18th to 20th of October, 2017.

This fair is held annually giving an opportunity to Chinese and international brands to present and launch their products to mainly Chinese national market, as well as to some International representatives.

Paola Reina organized a small meeting with the most interested clients and new partners who will represent the brand in the Chinese market, to inform them about ToyLabs and the participation of Industria Auxiliar Juema S.L., its manufacturer, in it. During the meeting, the concept of the project was explained, and what could be the benefits for new markets and customers. Most of the clients mentioned the importance of the exchange of the new technologies, experience, exchange of completely different tendencies in doll

design and an easy access to all of it as benefits of this platform.

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was agreed that more feedback will be from this group in due time, as the platform evolves and is in operational

Fall Toy Preview 2017in Dallas USA

Event information

Title: Fall Toy Preview 2017in Dallas USA

Date/Place: Dallas USA

Participation: V-Cubes

Action: Presentation to visitors

Fall Toy Preview 2017in Dallas USA. This is the biggest annual Show for pre-releases of Toys in North America. We showed and introduced ToyLabs in our partner booth.

Event information

Title: *Spiel International 2017*

Date/Place: October 2017. Essen-Germany

Participation: FV-Cubes

Action: Presentation to visitirs

Spiel International 2017

Spiel International 2017 in Essen-Germany. This is the biggest Toy Festival globally and is open for consumes and traders. We showed and introduced ToyLabs in our partner booth. We discussed and introduced the project once again to 7 European Toy makers.

PROGRAMA INMERSIÓN DIGITAL EMPRESARIAL (IDE) - REALIDAD VIRTUAL Y AUMENTADA

Event information

Title: Programa inmersión digital empresarial (IDE) – Realidad virtual y aumentada

Date/Place: Insonmnia building – Valencia. 4th October 2017

Participation: AIJU

Material: Presentation, Brochure and poster

Action: Presentation of the results in WP1 and WP2 and new business model, platform and how to collaborate in new developments.

Presentation: New business models for SME are using Augmented Reality. By Cesar Carrión

Attendees: 150 visitors form SME's form Valencian sector

<http://www.innsomnia.es/programa-inmersion-digital-empresarial>

Last 11th October in Valencia, TOYLABS was presented to around 150 Valencian SMEs by AIJU Team, on "Immersion Digital Empresarial" framework, The first immersion cycle designed only for presidents and CEOs of SMEs, led by the team with more experience in Spain in the analysis of the digital transformation of the industry. A great experience together with speakers like Nokia or Brainstorm

Experience was very successful because AIJU had the opportunity to work with multiple examples in companies, and Networking before and after the session

There was special interest on how to use the platform and how Augmented Reality can be used to communicate with childhood and safety experts.

Multiple examples in companies, news of innovation, vision of consulting, discussion between technology.

Contacts with great multinational technology companies were made also researchers from universities and technological institutes were interested and informed about the project.

AEFJ Preshow juguetes 2017-11-10

Event information

Title: *AEFJ Preshow juguetes 2017-11-10*

Date/Place: Villa Gadea– Altea. 6-9 November 2017

Participation: AIJU

Material: Presentation, Brochure and rollup

Action: Presentation of the project in relation with trend analytics

Presented by Maria Costa

Attendees: more than 43 Toy manufacturer SME's and 20 Toy

AEFJ Preshow Juguetes is a prestigious national event for the SME to show new products before the Christmas campaign. AIJU was present in such event as the research institute expert in toys and leisure product.

During the presentations, AIJU team introduced the project to the participants. The main content of the presentation was focused in early detection of trends as tool to an early access to the market. Other presented topics of great interest to the assistants were the new bussines model, toy developing methodology proposed by ToyLabs and Toylabs Colaborative Platform.

Audience has very interested in explotation of results topic such as if the platform was sustained by mensual fees or pay per use. Another important topic that created interterest were regarding data protection and ethical issues due to the high competence in the between toy SME's companies.

Toy manufacturers: Asivil, Artesanía Cerdá, Asler, Berjuan, Bonita Toys, Canal Toys, Cife, Claudio Reig, Comansi, DeQUBE, Educa Borrás, Epoch para Imaginar, Fábrica de Juguetes, Funrise, Game Movil, Gonher, Hasbro Iberia, Injusa, JC Toys, Juguetes Cayro, Juguetes Falomir, Juguetrónica, Ludilo, M. Llorens, Mattel, Millenium baby, Miniland, Muñecas Arias, Muñecas Guca, Muñecas Paola, Ninco, Nines Artesanals d'Onil, Pequetren, Run Run Toys, Science 4you, Simba, Smoby, Tavitoys, Toc Toys, Toy Partner, V-Tech y Worldbrands.

Toy Retailers: CPA, Abacus, El Corte Inglés, Jugatoys, Juguetilandia, Jupesa, Toys R Us, Jugueterías Reunidas, Demaretoys, Grupo JAC, Jugetes Panre, Juguettos, Toy Planet, Toy Sur, Cladellas, Juguetes Grego, Todojuguete y Jugueterías Reunidas.

3.2 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

Scientific publications allow an effective dissemination of the project results and development to more specific target groups, particularly specialized and expert audiences of the different sectors participating in ToyLabs project.

NTUA has prepared and submitted the following conference paper that is pending on review and acceptance:

"Empowering product co-creation approaches through Business Interoperability Concepts: The Toy Industry case", 9th International Conference on Interoperability for Enterprise Systems and Applications (IESA 2018) to be held on 22/3/2018 and 23/3/2018 in Berlin.

The paper presents the open innovation and co-creation methodology focusing on partner matching and how it can be a gateway to achieving business process interoperability in the toy industry.

3.3 COMMUNITY BUILDING/ ENGAGEMENT WITH STAKEHOLDERS

The different target audiences have different interests in the project and need different information, for this reason, all the dissemination and communication activities are carefully planned in order to reach to every stakeholder in the appropriate way to reach their expectative.

The main contact point with stakeholders up to date has been the participation in events, where face-to-face meetings with interested visitors has given the opportunity to provide enough personalized information.

Each of the partners has dedicated their assistance to events to contact to an specific profile, mainly matching their own profile, that is for example toy manufacturers have mainly contacted other toy manufacturers.

Overall the contacts with stakeholders have been successful and the number of interested organisation and individuals has potentially increased thanks to the different communication and dissemination activities.

3.4 SYNERGIES WITH PROJECTS

The objective of creating synergies with other projects is to encourage the knowledge exchange and mutual validation of results.

3.4.1 Projects with Synergies

SAMT SUDOE

SAMT SUDOE PROJECT aims at developing links and between enterprises, R&D centres, clusters, higher education and R&D+i governmental & regional institutions to promote new KET in SUDOE space.

In particular, the focus is to boost advanced productive systems through additive manufacturing and advanced materials including nanotechnology. Among its results there is a transnational collaborative platform that aims to ease the involvement of SMEs in R&D activities and collaboration among organisations.

PSYMBIOSYS

The PSYMBIOSYS project team presented the Sentiment Management Engine that was created as part of the project’s Symbiotic Innovation Management Platform to provide insight into the technical and methodological foundations that would be useful in the design and implementation of the Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis methodology of ToyLabs. Various informal meetings and calls took place between PSYMBIOSYS members, NTUA and SILO, including a presentation of the PSYMBIOSIS solution that also included AIJU.

Project “PSYMBIOSYS: Product-Service sYMBIOtic SYStems”. PSYMBIOSYS aims at improving the competitiveness of European Manufacturing industries by developing an innovative product-service engineering environment, symbolized by a five-pointed symbiosis star – design-production, product-service, knowledge-sentiment, EDA-SOA, business-innovation – and able to dramatically reduce the time-to-market of more attractive and sustainable product-service solutions

INVENT

Reinventing the Distribution and Delivery of Personal Services through Cloud Apps and Marketplaces (INVENT, National) – INVENT focuses on the generation of new knowledge to support the launch of innovative business models that capitalize the emergence of online marketplaces as intermediaries for distributing apps and cloud services.

PAASPORT

A Semantically-Enhanced Marketplace Of Interoperable Platform-As-A-Service Offerings For The Deployment And Migration Of Business Applications Of SMEs ([PAASPORT](#), FP7) – one of the primary objectives of PaasPort is to establish a pan-European Cloud marketplace, in order to provide the European Cloud PaaS vendors (in particular SMEs) the reference framework, and the enabling technologies and tools that will allow them to become part of a single, interoperable marketplace

NEMO

Hyper-Network for electroMobility ([NeMo](#), H2020) - NeMo will boost the market share of EVs by enabling increased accessibility to charging infrastructure, ICT services and wider B2B interconnectivity by creating common information models for objects, data and services.

3.4.2 Joint activities

AIJU PARTICIPATES IN A WORKSHOP SAMT SUDOE: MANUFACTURING THE FUTURE IN THE INDUSTRY 4.0

With about 100 participants, mostly coming from companies, it was held on last 18th May 2017 in CENTIMFE-Portugal, the **Technical Seminar on Additive Manufacturing and Advanced Materials: MANUFACTURING the FUTURE at INDUSTRY 4.0**.

AIJU participated in this event and presented ToyLabs among other projects related to the topic.

Event information

Title: Manufacturing the future at industry 4.0

Date/Place: 18th May 2017 in CENTIMFE-Portugal

Participation: AIJU

Material: Brochure, presentation

Attendees: 100 participants from companies

<http://www.samtsudoe.com/es/>

The topics were presented by the partners SAMT SUDOE Project; by a Member Company, an entity from the Scientific System and also a fund managing regional entity of Centro2020.

- SAMT PROJECT SUDOE, the developed activities, the achieved and expected results;
- Challenges and the Future of Additive Manufacturing in Industry 4.0;
- Metallic Additive manufacturing and advanced materials research highlights at Boudreaux;
- Additive Manufacturing of Metals: Challenges and Opportunities;
- Applications of Metal Laser Sintering

in the Mould Industry;

- Innovation Funding Opportunities.

The performed communications generated great interest from the participants who interacted with the speakers at the end of the session, the open point for questions.

During the event, was held a Show/Exhibition of Products and Additive Manufacturing Technologies which proved to be very interesting for the participants which participated simultaneously participated in a Matchmaking where they shared their expectations as regards to Additive Manufacturing Technologies and Advanced Materials, with a goal to share ideas that may be materialized in R&D+I project.

In AIJU's stand ToyLabs brochures were displayed and the project main objectives were presented to those interested in the idea. For more information, they were asked to visit the website or contact the partners. People showed great interest in the idea of a collaborative platform that includes additive manufacturing technologies as part of the new toys developing.

3.5 INTERNAL DISSEMINATION

Internally, all partners have disseminated the project in their organizations and through the internal communication channels.

SingularLogic

Internal cross-country presentations were held in Romania & Greece to familiarize the company's marketing department and technical divisions about the ToyLabs business concept and technologies. Adequate input has been provided to the marketing department in order to prepare targeted campaigns that will be gradually launched in several corporate communication channels (website, intranet, company's social media, press releases) during the following months. Internal workshops with the company's technical divisions were held in order to share technical know-how that can be used to commercial solutions.

Clustering with EU projects associated with the development of online marketplaces & ecosystems has been performed.

SingularLogic in collaboration with FabLab and Verdes Toys will target local toy manufacturing communities and 3d printing firms in Romania and Greece in order to disseminate the ToyLabs results. By approaching this network, SingularLogic will engage users for the project's pilot operations and contribute in the building of the ToyLabs SME community.

NTUA

NTUA presented the ToyLabs project on the post-graduate course "Special Management Subjects" as part of a speak about business interoperability.

Moreover, information about the project has been uploaded to the Decision Support Systems laboratory website.

An active effort was made to promote the project to professionals and organizations that collaborate with the Decision Support Systems laboratory, aiming to create further synergies, spark up interest and contact potential users of the platform.

AIJU

Internal presentations have been held in order to inform the different departments about the project. Getting all the areas involved in the project and well informed of the progress leads to a more coherent work. Moreover, if all the departments are informed of the project they are able to disseminate the project to their interested contacts.

AIJU launches its own Newsletter once every two months in both digital and printed versions. For the different issues, 700 copies are printed and distributed to partners, public entities and internal facilities and over 9.000 are sent by email to associate and non-associate professionals and companies in different countries (Spain, France, Italy, Germany, china, etc.).

Since the start of the project this issues have included articles informing of the concept and progress of ToyLabs. Apart from this, the organization website includes the link and description of ToyLabs in a section dedicated to projects. Through social media, AIJU's channels have shared ToyLabs information and posts.

V-CUBES

To promote the Project through the organization network, V-Cubes has published several Facebook and Twitter posts informing about the project and included information about the project in the organization website.

To directly promote the project, a personal e-mail was sent to 27 famous Toymakers in V-Cubes network informing about ToyLabs and asking to answer an on-line questionnaire about relevant and necessary information for the development of the project.

FABLAB Lecce

Fablab Lecce has developed various activities and strategies aimed to spreading and engaging the community in the Toylabs project.

We have sent an email to inform all our partners and customers what are the aims of the Toylabs project .

We have spoken about the proget during the event "Conversazioni sul Futuro", an event

Four days with almost 200 special guests involbved in about 90 appointment diffused in over 20 locations of Lecce (theaters, cultural centres, libreriyes, public place and schools) from Thursday the 26th to Sunday 29 th october.

We will distribute some gadgets to advertise the Toylabs Projects during the "Solidshow" event related to Innovation that will take place in Bari on November the 9th.

Likewise, we will organize for the "Maker Faire Rome" that will take place in Rome from the 1st to 3rd December and to which Fablab Lecce will participate.

We are attending students from primary to high schools in the School@Work Program, period while the kids and teenagers go to company to understand better the workwoldr.

During this project, we involve them in the Toylabs project by modelling and printing objects with the Toylabs logo.

On the other hand, we use to host students from international schools who are attending some weeks of internship at Fablab Lecce. Also those students are understanding the Toylabs project, modeling and printing some items.

During those events some products with the Toylabs logo printed on are realized and distributed during events and alternative projects.

FabLab Romania

In FabLab Romania, meetings have been performed to inform all the team about the project, it's stages and the expectations. The main dissemination activities performed have been related to plan and search suitable publication and events where the presentation of the project is interesting for the dissemination objectives.

The project has been presented to the clients in FabLab Romania facilities and all the visitors have been offered information through a mailing list.

Fablab Romania has reached several FabLabs to provide information about the project and gather feedback regarding their interest in participating in a project such ToyLabs.

Through the organisation social media all ToyLabs post have been shared and the interal dissemination activities were communicated.

JUEMA

Juema is the manufacturing company associated to Paola Reina, given this, the project was presented to the different teams in both companies to ensure maximum diffusion in the company.

The main communication channels that have been used for internal communication belong to Paola Reina, as JUEMA being an industrial company has not many. The companies associated with JUEMA and Paola Reina were informed of the project and their feedback was gathered.

4 UPDATED DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT PLAN

The dissemination during the first months of the project has consisted basically in making people aware of the project and the new methodology that was to be created. In that phase there were not many results to communicate therefore the dissemination activities were less intensive.

Henceforth, as there are there are more results to communicate and in depth information about the methodology, platform and pilots, all the communication activities have to be more exhaustive. All this is considered in the updated dissemination, communication and community engagement plan.

4.1 UPDATED DISSEMINATION PLAN

In the early dissemination plan the project was divided in three phases, based on that, currently the project is facing the end of the second phase and start of third phase, what this means is that the intensity of the dissemination activities has to be high and the content has to include the results of the project as they come.

To update the plan, information related to the impact and specific dissemination activities is going to be presented in a more exhaustive way.

Dissemination Mechanisms	BigDataOcean Phases		
	Phase I: Raise Awareness (M1-M6) Diss. Obj. I, III Activities' Intensity: Low Target Audiences: ALL	Phase II: Inform and Interact (M7-M12) Diss. Obj. I, II, III, IV Activities' Intensity: High Target Audiences: ALL	Phase III: Promote (M13-M18) Diss. Obj. II, III, IV, V, VI Activities' Intensity: High Target Audiences: ALL
(D1) Organisation of Project Events	D1.I) Organisation of workshops in scientific conferences	D1.II) Organisation of workshops in scientific conferences, industry events & fairs; Organisation of hackathon	D1.III) Organisation of workshops in industry events; Organisation of hackathon & demo events
(D2) Participation to Conferences & Workshops	D2.I) Participation to events; Presentation of project scope; Interaction with participants	D2.II) Presentation of project's results to events; Representation in booths	D2.III) Presentation of project's results and business case to events; Representation in demo sessions
(D3) Scientific Publications	D3.I) Publication of position papers / review papers in conferences	D3.II) Publication of methodology papers in conferences	D3.III) Publication of overall project's results in journals & industry magazines
(D4) Community Building / Engagement with Stakeholders	D4.I) Establishment of contact points; Liaison with industry communities and networks; Promotion of project's communication material; Interviews	D4.II) Validation of results with key stakeholders in events / online; Interaction with industry communities and networks; Invitation to project's events	D4.III) Creation of network of potential users; Promotion of project's application stories; Invitation for demos; Training webinars
(D5) Collaboration and synergies with projects	D5.I) Synergies identification; Establishment of contact points; Exchange of ideas & intentions	D5.II) Periodic bilateral exchange of news & results, Joint presence in events	D5.III) Joint engagement in events / demo days
(D6) Internal Dissemination in partner's networks	D6.I) Project's links & news in partners' website, social media accounts, newsletters	D6.II) Inclusion of projects' results in partners' events	D6.III) Demonstration of results in partners' premises; Training; Reuse of results

Figure 11 Early dissemination plan

D1 ORGANISATION OF PROJECT EVENTS

Regarding to the events organised by the consortium, two type of events are planned: demo events and workshops. This events will be held once the platform is ready to ensure a great promotion of the project results and increase the awareness.

Demo events

This events will consist on a demonstration of the project methodology and the functioning of the platform. With this presentations participants will be aware of the benefits that this new developing methodology could have in their own organisations. For this reason, this events are planned to be organised during the second year of the project, when the results of the project will be ready.

As different stakeholders will have different interests on the platform, all partners will organise and in-house demo event oriented to show the benefits that the platform has to offer to every specific profile. This will also ensure one event in each of the countries participating in the project.

The main objective of the events is to showcase the effectiveness of the platform and the new ToyLabs methodology, the perfect way to accomplish this objective will be to show the evolution of the pilots and how using the platform has benefit the company in the sense of a new business model and/or better products to bring to the market.

Workshops

ToyLabs presents a new toy developing methodology through a platform that allows collaborative design and production of the new toy that leads a series of improvements and benefits for the different parties. Thanks to the workshops, participants will be instructed in the new methodology, the functioning of the platform and all the benefits that come along.

It is planned to organise two workshops where representatives of the consortium will present and explain the project results to the audience in order to make them aware of the functioning of the new methodology and the platform. This events will be planted in an interactive manner so the participants not only will be able to learn the functioning of the platform but also experience how will this new methodology affect their own interests, for example, how a toy manufacturer could shorten the time to market of a new toy.

D2 PARTICIPATION IN CONFERENCES AND WORKSHOPS

In this phase of the Project, the participation in events is quite more important, with the results present, is now crucial to contact stakeholders and present the methodology and the platform along with business case.

Events represent the easiest way to directly contact interested stakeholders and provide them with personalised information of the project. For this reason, the events have to be carefully selected in order to reach the right audiences, these events will include a presentation of the results.

Demo booth

The project dissemination plan establishes that one demo booth has to be established in a fair. To accomplish this objective and get the best results from it, the fair where this will be performed is yet to be selected. Different factors are being taken into consideration for the selection of the event: Size and profiles of the audience, Recognition of the event, Cost of participation, Location, etc.

The demo booth will showcase the project results to the interested visitors and enough information will be provided. The aim is to get more organisation involved in the project and in future versions of the platform by showing the functionalities and benefits it provides.

Events participation plan

During the next months, partners have planned the participation in different events where the presentation of ToyLabs is interesting. During these events representatives of the consortium will inform the participants about the project and encourage them to become part of it or get more information. Different materials will be displayed depending on the type of event and the audience.

Title	Description	Location	Date	Website
CEBIT 2018	The biggest fair/ exhibition in Europe for Digital Business Attended by SLG	Hannover, DE	11-15 March 2018	https://www.cebit.de/en/
Spielwarenmesse International Toy Fair 2018	The biggest and most important Toy Fair worldwide. Attended by JUEMA, V-Cubes and AIJU	Nurnberg, Germany	31 January – 4 February 2018	www.spielwarenmesse.de
Preshow Noël Jouets & Jeux	THE annual meeting for toys & games sector in France Attended by AIJU	Deauville, France	20-24 november 2017	http://www.preshow-noel.fr/?lang=en
Museum Connections 2018 Paris.	Attended by V-Cubes	Paris, France	January 2018	
London Toy Fair 2018	Attended by V-Cubes	London, England	January 2018	https://www.toyfair.co.uk/
New York Toy Fair 2018	Attended by V-Cubes	NewYork, USA	February 2018	http://www.toyfairny.com/
Cannes Festival Des Jeux 2018	Attended by V-Cubes	Cannes, Francia	February 2018	http://www.festivaldesjeux-cannes.com/festival/introduction
Solid Show	Attended by Fablab Lecce	Bari – Italy	9 th November 2017	
Maker Faire Rome	Attended by Fablab Lecce	Rome – Italy	01-03 December 2017	http://www.makerfairerome.eu/it/
3 other makerfairs	Attended by Fablab Romania	To be confirmed	To be confirmed	

To collect feedback from the events in an organised way all the partners are asked to fill a reporting document, this documents are created so all partners are

informed of the activities performed in the scope of the project and to keep all this information and the feedback obtained organised. The template can be found bellow in Table 3

Reporting template for events

Type	Participation in Conference / Workshop
Organization of Conference / Workshop	
Event Name	
Venue	
Date	
Event objectives	
Size of audience (approx.)	
Dissemination Level	International, National/Regional/Local
Description of activity	
Title	The title of the presentation
Presenter	The name of the presenter
Other Partners Involved	In case your organisation collaborated with other partners for this activity you should indicate that here.
Type of Audience	
Hash tags for Social Media Dissemination	
URL	Provide a relevant URL for the event
Relevant Resources	Attachments such as: (filenames or URLs) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Photos • Agenda • Presentations
Material presented	Brochure/ presentation/ roll up
Feedback	Feedback received

Table 3 Reporting template for events

D3 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

Scientific publications represent the most adequate way to promote the results among scientific communities and facilitate the ideas' gathering and knowledge exchange with relevant communities and initiatives.

Different academic papers on the findings and advancements of the project will be submitted in the following months of the project.

The NTUA team intends to submit at least one more academic (journal or conference) paper by the end of 2017 more aligned towards the project's impact specifically to the creative industry.

In the first half of 2018, NTUA intends to submit at least 3 more academic papers incorporating the pilot's results and feedback from the industry, to describe the enhancements and rethinking of the methodology and the tools created that this process will bring. One is intended to focus on the results of the pilot operation and the conclusions drawn from the validation feedback, one on the updated methodology based on the pilot feedback, and one on the implementation of market trend analysis and social feedback analysis for the toy sector.

Regarding the publication of articles in industry magazines, it is expected to submit 6 articles, one per partner/country, this activity will start in 2018. All partners have to find interesting and accessible magazines where this articles could be submitted.

All the publications have to be reported to the consortium using the template presented in Table 4 Reporting template for publications Table 4

Reporting template for publications

Full citation	The full citation of the paper
Responsible	The person responsible for the paper, typically the first author.
Partners Involved	The name of the partners involved in this paper
Hash tags for Social Media Dissemination	
URL	
Attachments	The final version of the paper e.g. in pdf or doc, as well as a link to the presentation (ppt or pdf)
Feedback	Feedback received

Table 4 Reporting template for publications

D4 COMMUNITY BUILDING/ ENGAGEMENT WITH STAKEHOLDERS

This activity refers to the proper communication of the project and engagement of relevant stakeholders. It is very important to have a great network of stakeholders to whom the consortium could provide information regarding project news, events and results. This network could benefit the project by providing the means to validate the project concept, findings and advancements; ideas' gathering and knowledge exchange; Attraction of potential clients and adopters; increased awareness.

As it has already been explained the best way to contact stakeholders is through the participation in events. In this events, as it has been already done, consortium representatives will explain the project concept and results to the participants and encourage them to get involved in the project by participating or getting more information.

Webinars

It is planned to run two webinars in 2018 in line with major releases and advances in the project. The first one with the launch of the integrated platform in month 14 and a second one with the final version of the platform in month 18.

All those contacted in previous activities will be informed of these webinars and invited to join.

The webinars will include the launch of the platform and explanation of the different modules available and how to use them. A discussion will be held with participants' questions and interests.

D5 COLLABORATION AND SYNERGIES WITH PROJECTS

Finding other projects with common fields or topics is a great way to encourage the Knowledge exchange; Mutual validation of results; Joint dissemination activities; Attraction of potential partners for research collaborations. For this reason, the consortium aims to find other projects to create collaboration and synergies and plan joint activities.

Projects with synergies

Apart from those already listed above, all partners should find project with common fields with whom ToyLabs could establish synergies and enrich both projects. These synergies could be a matter of scientific research, validation of results, etc.

Joint activities

To create joint activities all these projects will be invited to join the events organised by ToyLabs where their intervention could be helpful to the objectives of the event. Likewise, ToyLabs representatives will attend events organised by other projects and provide interesting information that could enrich the vision of the event.

For any joint activity or collaboration in an event, a reporting template has to be completed in order to keep all the information organised and inform all the partners in the consortium about the outcomes of such participation.

Reporting template for collaboration activities

Type	Bilateral Meeting / Interaction in Event / Co-organization of Event / E-mail Communication
Title	The title of the collaboration activity
Projects Involved	Information about the projects involved
Venue	The location where the collaboration activity took place
Date	The date that the collaboration activity took place
Activity objectives	
Description	The location that the event took place
Expected/realized impact	Brief description of the impact materialized or expected by the collaboration action if already realized or assessable
Expected follow-up actions	Brief description of the follow-up actions to this collaboration activity
URL	Provide a relevant URL, if one exists
Partners Involved	In case your organisation collaborated with other partners for this activity you should indicate that here.
Relevant Resources	Attachments such as: (filenames or URLs) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Photos (at least 1) • Agenda • Presentations
Feedback	Feedback received

Table 5 Reporting template for collaborartion activities

D6 INTERNAL DISSEMINATION IN PARTNER'S NETWORKS

Internal partners' events

To promote the project locally, each partner will run an internal event. These events will present ToyLabs news and results in partners' networks. The feedback obtained will be used to validate the project concept, findings and advancements and encourage knowledge exchange and increase the awareness of the project.

In these events organised in-house each partner will present the project to their network. The presentation will include the purpose of the project and evolution along with the results: present the platform and explain the new methodology proposed by ToyLabs and how this new method will benefit the participants. The scope of the presentation will vary depending on the profile of the presenter and more important the assistants.

This activity will start in 2018, once the integrated platform has been launched, this way will be a great opportunity to present the main components and functionalities of the platform to interested target audiences.

Training sessions

To train the different companies in how to use the different platform modules and functionalities, two training sessions will be organised.

These sessions will give in depth information about the new methodology proposed by ToyLabs and how changing the traditional method can bring benefits to the different companies participating in the process. Along with the methodology, an intensive training will be provided in how to start and run a project through the platform step by step and how to make the most out of the functionalities that the platform offers.

In these sessions is planned to give the training to the toy makers in the consortium along with other companies interested. The trainings will be taught by NTUA and AIJU, one in each country.

The internal training sessions will be planned in 2018, as explained above, the integrated platform has to be ready in order to offer an appropriate training.

4.2 UPDATED COMMUNICATION PLAN

Just as in the dissemination plan, in the early communication plan the project was divided in three phases, based on that, currently the project is facing the end of the second phase and start of third phase, what this means is that the focus of each phase is diffuse knowledge and communication culmination respectively

To update the plan, information related to the impact and specific communication activities is going to be presented in a more exhaustive way.

Communication Mechanisms \ ToyLabs Phases	Phase I: Raise Awareness (M1-M6) <i>Comm. Obj. I, II, III, V</i>	Phase II: Diffuse Knowledge (M7-M12) <i>Comm. Obj. I, II, III, V</i>	Phase III: Communication Culmination (M13-M18) <i>Comm. Obj. I, II, III, IV, V, VI</i>
(C1) ToyLabs Website	C1.I) Design & Development of an intuitive and responsive project's web site; Search engine optimization	C1.II) Regular update of the website content; Watch website's analytics to measure impact and provide content of interest	C1.III) Regular update of the website content; Clear visibility of results, demo / application material in an interactive way
(C2) ToyLabs Social Media Presence	C2.I) Establishment of presence in: Reproduce relevant content and monitor relevant hashtags; Upload public material; Follow influencers of the domain; Engage with other projects and initiatives	C2.II) Promote project's outcomes and events; Interact with followers to get feedback; Answer on comments and private messages on the various channels; Upload public material; Reproduce relevant content and monitor relevant hashtags	C2.III) Promote project's outcomes and events; Interact with followers to get feedback; Answer on comments and private messages on the various channels; Upload public material; Reproduce relevant content (more sporadically)
(C3) ToyLabs Blog	C3.I) Deploy project's blog; Provide blog posts related to project's positioning & technologies	C3.II) Provide frequent blog posts to initiate discussions on specific issues relevant to the project to receive feedback	C3.III) Publish frequent blog posts to demonstrate and promote project's results
(C4) Traditional Media	C4.I) Press release to announce the project's launch	C4.II) Press releases to announce the significant events / results	C4.III) Press releases to promote the business case of the project's results
(C5) Communication Material	C5.I) Design logo and project identity; Prepare project factsheet, brochure, banner, e-Newsletter and promo video	C5.II) Prepare revised brochure, banner and frequent releases of e-Newsletter; Publish blogs / news in EU instruments (e.g. Cordis News, research*eu magazines etc.)	C5.III) Prepare final brochure, banner, frequent releases of e-Newsletter and video demonstrators; Publish blogs / news in EU dissemination instruments

Figure 12 Early communication plan

C1 TOYLABS WEBSITE

ToyLabs website was created at the start of the project and has been updated regularly including news and updated materials. For next steps the website content has to be updated regularly to include all the results in the project.

The project public website will include access to the platform when available and several materials related to the modules and functionalities of the platform.

The website will be regularly updated to ensure the visibility of the project in the main search engines, and will be promoted in different media to bring traffic to the website where people can find plenty of information about the project.

ToyLabs public website is where all the public information is gathered and where anyone interested can be fully informed about the project, for this reasons all the main communication and dissemination activities will direct to the website, including a call to action to find further information or contact the consortium.

C2 SOCIAL MEDIA PRESENCE

In the next phases of the project the social media presence has to increase in order to reach a wider audience and increase the engagement. To reach this objective a series of measures have to be taken:

- Be aware of the target audience: to engage the audience and increase the number of followers is important to know the information they need or would like to see published. To achieve this tools like Social Analytics will be used.
- Optimise the profiles: keep personalising the profiles, updated pictures shows a refreshed page for example, even more, all the social media channels are constantly updating their characteristics and offer new tools, taking advantage of these functionalities help to attract new public and engage the followers.
- Create and manage a calendar of content: for this purpose, the tool buffer has been used since the start of the project to organise and schedule the publications. For next phases this tool will continue to be used to schedule the publications taking into account the content and format. It is important to vary the format (images, video, text) to engage the public.
- Publish relevant information related to the project: provide consistent and continuous information adapted to the different social media channels will attract more public and boost the social media impact. To do this several publications regarding the progress of the project will be prepared when the project has reached a milestone, an event is organised, etc.
- Boost publications: there are some particularly interesting publications that is important that reach a wider audience and could lead to more followers. In these cases, publications will be boosted to increase the impact and improve the effectivity of the publication.

C3 TOYLABS BLOG

ToyLabs blog is the best way to communicate the main project concepts and advancements to a wide audience, using a catchy and easily understandable manner will attract all the target audience groups and provide them with enough information about the progress of the project.

Until now, different blog posts have been published according to the established plan. In the table below it is possible to see all the planned posts for the next months, responsible and deadlines. This table represents a plan that might be modified according to the best suitability for the project.

Title	Description	Date	State	Responsible
14. The Integrated ToyLabs Platform - V1	Input form D4.2	29/11/2017	In process	SLG
15. ToyLabs Partner Matching and Selection Methodology	Input from T2.4	14/12/2017	To be started	NTUA
16. Walkthrough Of the ToyLabs platform	Demo Scenario description	25/01/2018	To be started	SLG
17. Lessons Learned from 1st ToyLabs Demonstration period	Input from D5.2	14/02/2018	To be started	FABLAB Lecce
18. Presentation of the Final ToyLabs platform	ToyLabs platform presentation	29/03/2018	To be started	SLG
19. Final Lessons Learned from ToyLabs Demonstration period	Input from D5.3	30/05/2018	To be started	FABLAB Lecce
20. Outcomes and Key TakeAways from the ToyLabs project	Final outcomes of the project	28/06/218	To be started	AIJU+NTUA

Table 6 ToyLabs blog plan

To increase the interactions, the blog post will be shared in social media and viewers will be encouraged to comment give opinion or ask questions in the comment sections. The content has to be created in an attractive way that also encourages people to share and comment.

C4 TRADITIONAL MEDIA

Traditional media will be used to promote the project locally, for this reason every partner will find the best way to do this. Every partner should do on release in one of the traditional media: newspaper, radio, television, etc.

The content of the publication may vary depending on the time when the publication opportunity arises, but it must contain information about the concept and result of the project. Publications in traditional media would be useful to promote project events performed locally, workshops, webinars, etc.

C5 COMMUNICATION MATERIAL

Up to now, different materials have been developed to improve and make the communication of the project easy. Mainly, brochures and posters have been prepared for the presentation in events and trade fairs. All the materials designed follow the same visual style and create ToyLabs brand identity, for future materials, the style should be aligned to the existing but it can be adapted to better fit the different means of communication.

Factsheets, brochures and banners

Different versions of brochures have been created to better fit to each event, these brochures could serve as a template for future versions.

The information presented in each publication has to be adapted depending on the target audience of the event it is going to be presented at but always keeping in mind a unified style and the general content. This is very important to give the audience personalised information that will be attractive to them but with a unified experience.

At least two more brochures or factsheets are going to be designed and printed with content adapted to the main events and milestones in the project. However, if any partner feels the need of creating a specific material that would be a better fit for a specific occasion, they will inform AIJU who will prepare the design and incorporate the specific content provided by each partner.

Newsletters

To promote the results of the project periodical newsletters will be prepared with the most important and interesting information regarding each step forward of the project.

The main newsletters to be published are the integrated platform release and the final platform release as two of the most important milestones.

A template for the newsletter is available for all partners to use. It can be modified or adapted to the requirements of each issue but always following the same style and visual identity of ToyLabs.

Videos

To promote the project three videos have to be created. This activity will start in 2018 when the results of the project are closer. The thematic of the videos are related to the evolution of the project, the first video will be dedicated to explain the project in general focusing on the scope and objectives; the second video will be

dedicated to promotion the launch of the platform; finally the last video will be focused on the pilots and the impact of the project.

The videos will be shared in the different social media channels (YouTube, Facebook, Twitter...) and included in the website. Sharing videos is a more attractive way to share information with the different interested target audiences.